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Executive Summary

This report D4.1 is the first release document on the technical work conducted by Space4Good within Work Package 4 (WP4) of the INNO4CFIs project.

The report's primary focus centers on the significant advancements made in Above-ground Biomass (AGB) modeling through the application of satellite remote sensing and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. It provides a thorough exploration of both traditional and cutting-edge AGB estimation methods, with particular emphasis on the project's unique methodology and results concerning land cover, vegetation health indices, and biomass distribution. The study integrates comprehensive data and tools descriptions, emphasizing the utilization of geospatial data and software. Key outcomes and outputs from the first project release are outlined, including the development of a geospatial visualization platform.

The report concludes with references to fundamental literature and supplementary appendices detailing project-specific geospatial datasets and review papers. This research contributes to advancing environmental monitoring capabilities through integrated satellite data and AI-driven approaches in biomass estimation in agroforestry ecosystems.

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Glossary of terms

AGB - Above-ground Biomass
AI - Artificial Intelligence
ANN - Artificial Neural Networks
CHM - Canopy Height Model
DBH - Tree Diameter at Breast Height
DEM - Digital Elevation Model
DSM - Digital Surface Model
DTM - Digital Terrain Model
ESA - European Space Agency
EVI - Enhanced Vegetation Index
EWC - ESA World Cover
GEDI - NASA's Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation
GIS - Geographic Information System
INNO4CFIs - Innovations for Carbon Farming Initiatives
ISS - The International Space Station
LiDAR - Light Detection and Ranging
LR - Linear Regression
MODIS - Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NASA - National Aeronautic and Space Agency
NDVI - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI - Normalized Difference Water Index
NFIs - National Forest Inventories
NIR - Near-Infrared
NLP - Natural Language Processing
Radar - Radio Detection and Ranging
RF - Random Forest
RGB - Red, Green and Blue
R² - Coefficient of Determination
RMSE - Root Mean Squared Error
SAR - Synthetic Aperture Radar
SVM - Support Vector Machine
SWIR - Shortwave Infrared
UAV - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
USGS - U.S. Geological Survey
VHR - Very High Resolution
WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 INNO4CFIs Project and Work Package 4

The European INNO4CFIs (Innovations for Carbon Farming Initiatives) project, titled "Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging Innovations to Enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives while Preserving Biodiversity, Water Security, and Soil Health," aims to advance carbon farming initiatives by integrating cutting-edge technologies. These technologies include desalination, mycelium-based phytoremediation, blockchain, and remote sensing solutions. The project is implemented across four living hubs (in detail in Appendix A) located in Italy, Greece, Spain, and Belgium, fostering the adoption of innovative practices in carbon farming to ensure environmental sustainability and resilience.

WP4 has three main objectives:

1. Introducing satellite observations and AI technologies;
2. Measuring the difference pre and post AI and satellite monitoring, according to the KPIs defined in WP3;
3. Validating the integration of remote sensing, geographic information services and AI

In this context, Space4Good has developed a comprehensive document outlining a proposed methodology for remote sensing data collection and analytics using satellites data. This document is the first release and it outlines various methods designed to adapt to the specific needs and goals of the project, with the ultimate objective of providing the essential data input required for the carbon sequestration models being developed. Towards the end of the project a second release will be provided with final methodology and results.

The specific KPIs that can be measured via satellite observations are as follows: Vegetation indices, Tree cover, Canopy Height, Living Hub Extension/Location, Soil types, Land Cover and AGB. Together, all these satellite-based data/layers are essential to assess the carbon storage of the agroforestry practices.

1.2 Fundamentals of Satellite Remote Sensing

Satellite remote sensing involves acquiring information about Earth's surface without direct contact, using satellites equipped with sensors. This cutting-edge technology has brought a significant transformation in our approach to monitoring major ecosystems across the globe. It offers the advantage of delivering near real-time data with adaptable spatial and temporal scales, fundamentally altering our ability to study and understand natural environments. By utilizing these tools, users can access high-resolution information related to land use, vegetation cover, and carbon storage, all of which are critical components for estimating carbon emissions and sequestration. International organizations and their methodologies for carbon accounting have started to acknowledge the crucial role that remote sensing technologies play in this field, as demonstrated by studies such as those conducted by Kumar & Mutanga (2017) and Yan et al. (2023). These technologies have been consistently proven as efficient, reliable, and replicable methods for quantifying and monitoring carbon capture.

The quantity of carbon stored in a forest is intrinsically linked to the amount of biomass present. Satellite imagery is equipped with multispectral sensors, which can be utilized to derive vegetation indices, serving as a proxy for estimating biomass. Modern satellite missions, such as the Sentinel-1 and the GEDI (NASA's Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) instrument, provide diverse types of data that facilitate biomass quantification due to their distinct sensors. Drones are equally versatile, as they can be equipped with a wide range of sensors, including high-resolution cameras, multispectral and hyperspectral sensors, and LiDAR technology. Both these technologies are capable of capturing valuable information that can be tailored to meet the specific needs and requirements of any given project. In this specific technical report, we will focus on the Satellite technology, data and methodology.

Remote sensing data can be broadly classified into two primary categories: Passive Sensors, which encompass instruments such as multispectral and hyperspectral sensors, and Active Sensors, which include radar and LiDAR technologies. These distinctions are visually represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Remote sensing sensor type based on energy source (Wikimedia, 2013).

Passive remote sensing sensor systems (Figure 1 - top) acquire images of the earth based on sun reflectance to objects on earth. This reflectance is actually a spectrum of electromagnetic waves that can be seen by humans such as red, green and blue (RGB) light in wavelengths 400 - 550 nanometer (nm) or the one that cannot be seen but feels like infrared (>600 nm). While using RGB, we might see earth just like we see using our own eyes, using another spectrum such as infrared, it can give more information.

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Figure 2: Spectral reflectance curve characteristics from multiple objects.

Different objects have distinct responses to light, which leads to their unique appearance when perceived by human eyes or remote sensing instruments. This variability is due to the way objects absorb, reflect, and emit electromagnetic radiation across different wavelengths. E.g in the near infrared spectrum, sun energy is reflected highly by stomata in the leaf, therefore, it has a high reflectance. This allows us to see better vegetation level, intensity, or diversity. It is also the case in short wavelength infrared, where the effect can be seen in soil or buildings. This insight is known as the spectral reflectance curve as in Figure 2.

Active remote sensing (Figure 1 - bottom) involves sensors that emit their own energy towards the Earth's surface and then detect the reflected or backscattered signals. This allows active sensors to operate independently of external light sources, enabling data acquisition regardless of time of day or weather conditions (Jensen, 2007). Unlike passive sensors, active sensors can function effectively in darkness and under cloudy conditions - they become essential when working in tropical/subtropical areas where cloud coverage is a great limitation. Examples of Active Sensors are Radar and LiDAR.

Both passive and active satellite systems play a crucial role in biomass assessment, providing valuable insights into the distribution and dynamics of vegetation on a large scale. By utilizing various remote sensing techniques, such as multispectral, LiDAR or radar data, satellites can estimate biomass levels in forests, croplands, and other ecosystems (Tian et al., 2023). These assessments are vital for understanding carbon cycles, ecosystem health, and climate change mitigation efforts. Examples of remote sensing data and how the biomass predicted would look like can be observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Using remote sensing data: multispectral imagery visualizes using standard false color (top-left) and canopy height generated from digital surface model (DSM) and digital terrain model (DTM) (top-right) to model biomass (bottom).

However, in order to ensure accurate and reliable satellite-based biomass assessments, field collection becomes imperative. In fact, the spatial and temporal resolution of satellites is relatively coarse, making it essential to gather data on the ground for validation purposes. Field collection involves on-ground measurements of vegetation attributes, such as tree diameter, height, and biomass, using established sampling techniques. This data serves as ground truth information, enabling the calibration and validation of satellite-derived biomass estimates (Chave et al., 2019). Once the observed and estimated biomass values reach a desired accuracy, the predictive models can be applied to estimate biomass in areas where in-situ measurements are not available.

Data Types

Multispectral Data

Multispectral data refers to imagery captured by sensors that measure electromagnetic radiation across multiple spectral bands. Typically, these bands encompass the visible, near-infrared (NIR), and sometimes additional bands in the shortwave infrared (SWIR) region. Multispectral sensors capture reflected or emitted energy from the Earth's surface, enabling analysis and interpretation of information across various wavelengths. Figure 4 shows the specific wavelength for each one of the data mentioned above.

Figure 4: corresponding wavelength for specific sensors.

These satellites offer numerous advantages for remote sensing applications. They acquire data in multiple spectral bands, facilitating the identification and analysis of different land cover types, vegetation health, and environmental parameters. This capability enables precise monitoring of crops, forests, and natural resources. Multispectral imagery also provides high-resolution spatial data, enhancing mapping and classification capabilities. Nevertheless, multispectral data has its limitations, including susceptibility to cloud cover, atmospheric interference, and restricted temporal resolution. Effective interpretation and analysis also necessitate sophisticated data processing techniques. Table 1 reports an overview of the most common free and commercial multispectral data.

Table 1: Free and commercial multispectral data overview.

Source	Satellites	Spatial Resolution	Applications	Access
Free Multispectral Satellite Data				
Landsat Program (NASA/USGS)	Landsat 8, Landsat 9, earlier missions	30m for visible and NIR, 15m for panchromatic, 100m for thermal	Environmental monitoring, agriculture, LULC mapping	USGS EarthExplorer, Google Earth Engine

Sentinel-2 (European Commission/ESA)	Sentinel-2A, Sentinel-2B	10m for visible and NIR, 20m for red edge and SWIR, 60m for atmospheric correction	Agriculture, forestry, land use, water bodies	Copernicus Open Access Hub, Google Earth Engine
MODIS (NASA)	Terra, Aqua	250m to 1km depending on band	Large-scale environmental and climate monitoring	NASA Earthdata, Google Earth Engine
VIIRS (NOAA/NASA)	Suomi NPP, NOAA-20	375m to 750m depending on band	Environmental monitoring, wildfires, vegetation health, SST	NOAA CLASS, NASA Earthdata
Commercial Multispectral Satellite Data				
DigitalGlobe/Maxar Technologies	WorldView-3, WorldView-4, GeoEye-1	Up to 30cm for panchromatic, 1.24m for multispectral	Precision agriculture, urban planning, disaster response, defense	Maxar Technologies
Planet Labs	PlanetScope, RapidEye	3-5m for PlanetScope, 5m for RapidEye	Agriculture, forestry, land use, environmental monitoring	Planet Labs
Airbus Defence and Space	SPOT 6, SPOT 7, Pleiades-1A, Pleiades-1B, Pleiades Neo 3, Pleiades Neo 4	1.5m to 6m for SPOT, 50cm for Pleiades, 30cm for Pleiades Neo Panchromatic, 1.2m for Pleiades Neo Multispectral	Urban planning, agriculture, forestry, environmental monitoring	Airbus Defence and Space
BlackSky	Global constellation of small satellites	~1m	Real-time monitoring, urban development, disaster response	BlackSky

Radar Data

Radar, an abbreviation for Radio Detection and Ranging, is a remote sensing technique that employs radio waves to detect and measure properties of objects and surfaces on the Earth's surface. Radar sensors emit radio waves and gauge the time it takes for these waves to return after interacting with the target, classifying it as an active remote sensing technology. Radar data can be collected through spaceborne, airborne, or ground-based radar systems.

Radar satellites offer numerous advantages in remote sensing. Their active sensing capability enables them to penetrate clouds, foliage, and darkness, ensuring all-weather and day-night imaging. However, they have limitations, as radar images lack the color and

texture details found in optical imagery, which restricts their utility in specific applications. In essence, interpreting radar images requires a deep understanding of the various bands that constitute a radar sensor and how these wavelengths impact different types of surfaces. Table 2 reports examples of notable satellite radar systems.

Table 2: Free and commercial multispectral Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data overview.

Source	Satellites	Radar Type	Applications	Key Features
Copernicus Programme (European Commission/ESA)	Sentinel-1 (A/B)	C-band SAR	Land and sea monitoring, mapping, disaster response	5m x 20m spatial resolution, all-weather, day-and-night capability
Canadian Space Agency (CSA)/MDA	RADARSAT-2	C-band SAR	Ice monitoring, agriculture, forestry, disaster management	1m to 100m spatial resolution, various imaging modes
Airbus Defence and Space/German Aerospace Center (DLR)	TerraSAR-X/TanDEM-X	X-band SAR	Urban mapping, topography, disaster monitoring	1m spatial resolution, high-resolution, 3D mapping capabilities
JAXA (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency)	ALOS-2 (Advanced Land Observing Satellite-2)	L-band SAR	Forestry, disaster monitoring, land use and land cover	3m to 100m spatial resolution, improved forest and disaster monitoring capabilities
ASI (Italian Space Agency)	COSMO-SkyMed (1-4)	X-band SAR	Earth observation, environmental monitoring, security and surveillance	High spatial resolution, multi-mode imaging
Hispasat/Spanish Ministry of Defense	PAZ	X-band SAR	Environmental monitoring, security, surveillance	High-resolution, dual-use for commercial and military purposes
CONAE (Argentinian Space Agency)	SAOCOM 1A/1B	L-band SAR	Agriculture, forestry, hydrology, disaster management	High spatial resolution, capable of penetrating vegetation, soil, and water surfaces
ISRO (Indian Space Research Organisation)	RISAT-1 (Radar Imaging Satellite-1)	C-band SAR	Agriculture, forestry, disaster management	3m to 50m spatial resolution, multi-mode imaging

NASA/ISRO	NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR Mission)	L-band and S-band SAR	Earthquake, volcano, and landslide monitoring	Dual-frequency, high-resolution, launching in 2024
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LiDAR Data

Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) is an active remote sensing technology that uses laser light to measure distances and create precise, three-dimensional information about the shape and surface characteristics of the Earth. LiDAR sensors can be mounted on various platforms, including terrestrial, mobile, airborne (UAV/plane), and satellite systems. This report focuses on spaceborne LiDAR, which offers unique advantages for large-scale and global observations.

LiDAR offers several advantages in remote sensing. It provides highly accurate three-dimensional measurements of the Earth's surface and objects, enabling detailed mapping of terrain, vegetation, and urban structures. It operates independently of daylight and captures high-resolution data and it can penetrate forest canopies, providing accurate measurements of the ground surface and vegetation structures beneath. Nonetheless, there are limitations to LiDAR remote sensing, including the relatively high cost of acquiring and processing data, which restricts its widespread use. Additionally, LiDAR is sensitive to atmospheric conditions, such as fog and dust, which can impact its performance. The small size of the newly planted trees represents another limitation. The interpretation and analysis of LiDAR data also necessitate specialized expertise and software tools.

Key examples of LiDAR data sources include the National Elevation Dataset (managed by the USGS and provides high-resolution elevation models covering the United States) and GEDI, an instrument mounted on the International Space Station (ISS) and operational since 2019.

1.3 Fundamentals of AI for Biomass

AI refers to the intelligence exhibited by non-living entities such as computers, robots, or other created objects (Hunt, 2014). Proposed as an academic discipline in 1956, it had earlier foundations in the work of Alan Turing, who referred to it as Machine Intelligence. Since its inception, the field of AI has evolved significantly and has gained widespread recognition among the general public in the 2020s. AI is utilized for decision-making,

planning, knowledge retrieval, writing, drawing, and other tasks expected of intelligent entities.

Despite its widespread use, the development and comprehension of AI are restricted to a relatively small number of individuals due to its advanced nature and the requisite expertise in computer science and statistics. This is particularly true for advanced AI techniques such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), transformers, and Natural Language Processing (NLP). However, certain areas of AI, such as classical machine learning models and techniques including linear regression (LR), support vector machines (SVM), and random forest (RF) models, have been widely adopted by researchers and professionals for decades to predict, regress, and classify statistical data.

AI methods have been extensively applied in various research domains, particularly in biomass modeling and prediction (Figure 5). Typically, multispectral and elevation data serve as predictors, while field data on biomass act as labels. This approach (Figure 5 - left) is commonly known as the semi-empirical method of biomass modeling. In addition to direct use of multispectral and elevation data, derived data such as spectral indices, forest canopy density, or texture may also serve as predictors. SAR data is occasionally employed as a predictor due to its capability to depict topography effectively.

Figure 5: Two approaches of machine learning to model biomass using remote sensing.

An alternative method for biomass modeling involves utilizing pre-generated land cover or species type maps, which may have been produced through machine learning or other techniques, and then converting these land cover classifications into biomass values based on established literature and sources. While this approach may lead to over-generalization,

it is beneficial for large-scale mapping, such as at the national level, due to its reduced requirement for extensive sample data. However, generating accurate land cover maps still necessitates a substantial number of samples. Numerous studies have employed AI and remote sensing for biomass modeling, leveraging diverse data types such as multispectral, RADAR, and LiDAR, and various models, including LR, RF, and SVM. Reviews by Galidaki (2017) and Eisfelder (2012) specifically examine these approaches in Mediterranean landscapes. The methodologies and results vary significantly depending on the location, species, and climate. The accuracy of biomass models is influenced by the choice of model, the quantity and quality of samples, and the features used. Additionally, the scale of analysis, whether focusing on individual trees or entire forests, plays a crucial role. The features or data types used in machine learning predictions are as critical as the sample data. Incorporating multiple types or sources of data can enhance predictive accuracy, provided there is a correlation with the field samples. Important features for biomass prediction using machine learning include canopy density, canopy height, and vegetation indices. Canopy height, in particular, is a vital feature due to its direct relationship with vegetation volume, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Correlation (R²) between canopy height and biomass of different vegetation types (Cunliffe, 2022).

1.4 DCAI 2024 Review Paper

To provide a comprehensive review, based on recently published papers and comparing information regarding AGB modeling, data sources, methodology, and model accuracy, Space4Good and Fondazione Amaldi worked on a review paper to be presented at the DCAI Conference 20204 in Salamanca, Spain. The paper by Ramadhan et al. (2024) is focused on utilizing high-resolution surface reflectance data acquired from commercial satellites for index and feature derivation. It resulted that integrating DSM and DTM derived from LiDAR, or SAR data, enhances the accuracy of the biomass prediction. AI models, such as RF, excel in incorporating multiple features, thus adeptly capturing sample characteristics for AGB estimations (read the full review paper in Appendix B).

2. AGB Modelling Pre and Post Satellite Remote Sensing and AI technologies

This chapter aims to review how forest AGB estimation is conducted following the development and implementation of remote sensing techniques and machine learning methods, reflecting the innovative approaches championed by INNO4CFIs. By examining these innovative methods, the review seeks to highlight how technological advancements are shaping the future of sustainable forest management and carbon farming.

2.1 Traditional Methods of Forest AGB Estimation (Pre)

Field measurement of forest AGB can be either destructive or non-destructive. The destructive method is to physically harvest the tree at ground level and weigh the dry biomass by component in a laboratory. Destructive measurements provide baseline data that is essential for developing allometric equations and calibrating remote sensing mapping, which are applied in non-destructive biomass estimation (Schwartz et al., 2023). Despite its importance for obtaining accurate data, the process can be time-consuming, labor-intensive, and costly (Salazar Villegas et al., 2023). Because of its intensive nature, destructive field measurement is typically limited to time and space, making the data unavailable or non-existent for wider regions due to its incomplete coverage (Wai et al., 2022). More importantly, destructive sampling can negatively affect the biodiversity and ecosystem functions of the sampled forest. Therefore, it is meaningful to explore non-destructive ways of measuring forest AGB that are efficient and reliable combining with field data.

Species-specific allometric equations allow for efficient and accurate calculations of tree biomass in a non-destructive way. These equations are mathematical formulas developed to estimate the individual tree biomass based on easily measurable tree parameters, specifically tailored for a particular tree species (Urbana et al., 2018). Commonly used parameters include tree diameter at breast height (DBH), tree height and wood density. The allometric equations often take a power-law form derived from empirical data collected through direct surveys and are applied on forest inventories (George-Chacón et al., 2022). Forest inventories consist of systematic tree parameters (DBH, height, age, crown features etc.), plot information (plot location and size, topography, soil and climatic variables etc.)

and forest attributes (tree density, basal area, biomass and carbon stocks etc.). Among them, National Forest Inventories (NFIs) are large-scale surveys designed to assess forest resources at national level. NFIs provide comprehensive data on forest composition, structure and health that are critical to conservation policy development and forest management. Forest inventories at national or regional scales have been widely used for forest AGB modeling as calibration data (Schwartz et al., 2023).

2.2 Innovative Methods of Forest AGB Estimation (Post)

Monitoring and understanding the spatial and temporal dynamics of forest AGB is the very critical step in quantifying carbon stocks and fluxes from forests (Salazar Villegas et al., 2023). Traditional field measurements on forest AGB are important and irreplaceable despite its limitations such as cost and coverage. These limitations can be compensated by utilizing remote sensing techniques and artificial intelligence modeling. Satellite-based observation techniques have become highly effective for monitoring and predicting AGB across various landscapes (Yan et al., 2023). These techniques leverage multiple spatial, temporal, and spectral resolutions, enabling detailed and comprehensive analysis of forest AGB (Wai et al., 2022).

Satellite sensors offer data at different spatial resolutions, from coarse (e.g., MODIS) to fine (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel-2) and very high resolution (e.g., Worldview, Pleiades). This range allows for monitoring AGB in diverse landscapes, from broad forest to small agricultural plots. High-resolution imagery is particularly valuable for detecting fine-scale variations in biomass, such as those caused by small disturbances or management practices. The frequent revisit times of many satellites enable continuous monitoring of AGB. This temporal resolution is vital for capturing seasonal variations in biomass, detecting changes due to climatic events, and monitoring the impacts of human activities like logging or agriculture (Ioki et al., 2014). It allows for the construction of time-series data to track trends and predict future biomass changes. Multispectral sensors can capture data across a few broad wavelength bands, including visible, NIR, and SWIR. Different land covers and vegetation types reflect and absorb light differently across these bands, allowing for vegetation and non-vegetation area distinguishing and the land cover detection. Additionally, vegetation indices correlated with greenness and health such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) are derived from multispectral data and can be proxies for biomass density.

Apart from passive sensors, active sensors such as LiDAR and SAR significantly enhance the capabilities for monitoring AGB. The ability of LiDAR to penetrate the canopy to some extent allows for a detailed analysis of forest structure and understory vegetation. Similarly, SAR utilizes microwave signals to image the Earth's surface, offering the advantage of data acquisition irrespective of weather conditions or sunlight availability. This feature is particularly beneficial in regions with persistent cloud cover. SAR data captures information about the surface roughness and dielectric properties of vegetation, which correlate with biomass (Liang et al., 2023). These technologies collectively enhance the capacity to monitor and manage biomass across various landscapes and environmental conditions, thereby improving the accuracy and efficacy of biomass estimation and related ecological studies.

Multi-source datasets including optical imagery, LiDAR and SAR have been combined in research on AGB modeling particularly through the application of machine learning techniques in recent years. The integration of satellite-based data sources and machine learning methods have provided further chances to improve the accuracy of forest AGB estimates over a broader area (Yan et al., 2023). Machine learning methods are widely used in the development of AGB research as they are adaptive to new data and complex patterns, with interpretable models providing clear insights into how input variables influence biomass predictions. Machine learning methods can be divided into supervised and unsupervised categories. Supervised learning uses training datasets to depict the relationship between input and output data, for example, decision trees, neural networks and SVM (Rodríguez-Veiga et al., 2019). Whereas unsupervised learning classifies a large sample of the subject by data analysis without category information, such as principal component analysis and cluster analysis. Most recently, Schwartz et al. (2023) used a deep-learning model based on remote sensing measurements (GEDI Lidar data and Sentinel-1 satellite imagery) to create a 10m resolution canopy height map of France for 2020. Then, they created a 30m resolution AGB density map of France with allometric equations fitted to the French NFIs plot data. Their results highlighted that coupling remote sensing technologies with recent advances in AI can generate insights into forest AGB estimation, which can significantly benefit forest management and related climate policies (Schwartz et al., 2023). Omoto et al. (2023) presented a new forest AGB map for the Brazilian Amazon using the largest airborne LiDAR data ever collected in the Amazon. The map utilized the airborne LiDAR data calibrated by field forest inventories that are extrapolated to the region using a machine learning method with inputs from SAR image,

vegetation indices obtained from the MODIS satellite and the precipitation data. The unique combination of datasets represented a better and more comprehensive understanding of regional forest biomass and structure, which overcame the inaccessibility of field trips and insufficient forest inventory data in the Amazon (Omoto et al., 2023). These studies illustrate how innovations in remote sensing and machine learning can address significant challenges in forest biomass estimation.

2.3 Discussion

The selection of a proper satellite data source is very important for mapping AGB precisely for specific study areas and periods of time. The spatial and temporal resolution and accessibility of the satellite data source are all important criteria. Mapping forest AGB at lower resolutions but across broader spatial extents is of paramount importance for several reasons. Large-scale research facilitates a comprehensive understanding of forest AGB dynamics on both global and regional scales. This macroscopic perspective is essential for identifying and monitoring extensive environmental changes and trends that may not be apparent in smaller, high-resolution studies. This approach is particularly critical for less developed countries, where natural resources are abundant but economic conditions are poor, and industrial activities dominate. In these regions, the infrastructure and resources necessary for detailed, localized studies are often lacking, making large-scale AGB data indispensable for effective resource management and policy making. Understanding the spatial distribution and health of forests in these areas is crucial for guiding sustainable development and conservation efforts, ensuring a balance between economic growth and environmental stewardship.

High-resolution satellite data sources and advanced surveying techniques, such as drone-based or terrestrial LiDAR, enable precise and efficient AGB estimates at fine scale. Fine-scale AGB mapping can produce highly accurate results when combined with forest inventory data and ancillary datasets such as rainfall, terrain, and temperature. This granularity allows for a detailed understanding of forest structure and biomass distribution, essential for effective forest management and conservation strategies. Moreover, fine-scale estimates facilitate real-time monitoring of forest dynamics, crucial for detecting and responding to changes in forest health, such as disease outbreaks, pest infestations, and climate change impacts. This capability is instrumental in building systems to supervise and combat illegal logging activities, allowing authorities to quickly identify and address unauthorized logging, thereby protecting valuable forest resources. Additionally,

detailed AGB data supports better decision-making for forest management, enabling the planning of sustainable harvesting practices, assessing conservation efforts' effectiveness, and making informed land use and forest restoration decisions. Accurate fine-scale AGB mapping is also essential for precise carbon stock assessments, critical for carbon accounting, carbon trading schemes, and supporting international climate agreements aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, fine-scale data helps in understanding habitat structures and biodiversity distribution within forests, valuable for designing and implementing biodiversity conservation strategies and identifying critical habitats requiring protection. It enables the assessment of forest resilience to climate change, allowing the development of strategies to enhance forest adaptation and mitigate adverse impacts. Lastly, high-resolution AGB data allows for more efficient allocation of resources for forest management and conservation, ensuring that efforts and funding are directed to areas where they are most needed, maximizing the impact of conservation initiatives.

There is widespread consensus among studies that the most accurate estimates of forest AGB are achieved through the integration of field survey data and remote sensing data. Consequently, numerous studies have utilized this combined approach to estimate forest AGB at local, regional, and global scales, employing a variety of algorithms (Zhang et al., 2020). Selecting an appropriate machine learning algorithm is crucial for the estimation and prediction of biomass. For instance, RF is an ensemble model that combines a large number of regression trees where each decision tree is constructed with a random set of features and samples and is learned independently of each other (Pal, 2005). The results of each tree are then combined to make the final prediction. This ensemble learning method offers the advantage of being non-parametric, dealing with dimensional data problems, and preventing the overfitting of models (Salazar Villegas et al., 2023). For the non-linear regression methods, SVR is a kernel-based algorithm commonly used for retrieving biophysical parameters from remote sensing data. Studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in estimating forest AGB (Liu et al., 2017). With the advancements in neural networks, deep regression networks hold significant potential for regression tasks. Algorithms such as ANN can establish complex nonlinear relationships and provide more accurate AGB estimates, particularly when ancillary variables like topographic factors are incorporated (Gao et al., 2018). In summary, the integration of multiple data sources and the selection of suitable algorithms and variables are critical steps for enhancing the

accuracy of AGB remote sensing estimation. This is especially important in areas characterized by high vegetation heterogeneity and complex geography.

Future research on forest AGB estimation should focus on integrating diverse satellite data sources, such as optical, radar, and LiDAR, to enhance model accuracy by capturing various forest characteristics comprehensively. Advancements in machine learning algorithms, particularly deep learning and ensemble methods, hold promise for improving predictive capabilities; novel algorithms based on the logic of RF should be explored for modeling complex forest structures. Additionally, utilizing time-series satellite data for temporal analysis and change detection can provide valuable insights into forest dynamics and the impacts of environmental changes, aiding long-term forest management and conservation efforts. Incorporating environmental and climatic variables, such as soil moisture, temperature, and precipitation, into AGB estimation models can further refine their accuracy. Moreover, establishing robust frameworks for integrating these advancements with reliable field data measurements will be crucial for enhancing the reliability and applicability of AGB models across diverse ecosystems.

3. Data & Tools Description

This chapter presents the data and tools utilized in the project as of the time of this report (for major information refer to chapter 1.2).

3.1 Project Data

To fulfill the WP4 goals of INNO4CFIs project utilizes the following remote sensing data:

- **Airbus Pleiades Multispectral Data**

Airbus Pleiades is a very high resolution (VHR) satellite imagery with 4 multispectral bands (blue, green, red, and NIR) in 2-meter resolution and 1 panchromatic band in 0.5-meter resolution. For mapping small areas of trees in agroforestry, VHR imagery is essential to detect individual trees due to their small size. In the Italian Living Hub of Follonica, Space4Good has tasked five new acquisitions with a recurrent time of 3-months period using the UP42 platform (<https://up42.com/>). These acquisitions require orthorectification (correction for geometric distortions and straight nadir viewing), pan-sharpening (enhancement of multispectral data using the panchromatic band), and surface reflectance radiometric correction (necessary for indices calculation and spectral manipulation processing).

Use within the project: map tree density, vegetation indices, land cover and as a baseline for AGB.

- **Vexcel Datasets**

Vexcel provides geospatial data products characterized by high accuracy, spatial resolution, and consistency. The Vexcel Data Program, the largest of its kind globally, captures ultra-high-resolution imagery (ranging from 5.5 to 15 cm resolution) and related geospatial data across more than 30 countries. Vexcel generates processed LiDAR into Digital Terrain Model (DTM) that shows the ground elevation surface and Digital Surface Model (DSM) which also include objects above the ground elevation. Subtracting DSM with DTM, you can have a canopy height model (CHM) which shows tree height. It's a commercial product.

Use within the project: create tree height, DTM and DSM layers.

- **GEDIL4A**

GEDI is a NASA mission that aims to study the Earth's forests and vegetation using lidar technology launched in December 2018. It is mounted on the ISS and uses a powerful laser system to measure the height and structure of forests globally. By sending laser pulses and measuring their return time, GEDI creates highly detailed 3D maps of forest canopy height, canopy structure, and vertical biomass distribution. These measurements help scientists understand the role of forests in the Earth's carbon cycle, ecosystem dynamics, and biodiversity. GEDI data enhances our understanding of the impacts of deforestation, forest degradation, and climate change on terrestrial ecosystems. It has a spatial resolution of 25m and a variable revisiting time since it accompanies the orbit of the ISS. All GEDI data collection is freely available to the public and covers the period from January 2019 to January 2023 when the mission was paused by NASA.

Figure 7: GEDI data visualized in light yellow to dark green on top of Landsat 8 567 composite in mangrove region, Sembilang National Park, Indonesia.

GEDI data differs from most remote sensing data in that it does not provide full scene coverage but instead records specific points along its path. This is illustrated in Figure 7, where GEDI data appears as strip lines across the landscape. Consequently, GEDI data is more suitable for use as samples or ground truth in modeling rather than direct application like other satellite imagery data.

For this project, we utilize GEDI L4A data to model AGB. The L4A dataset includes an agb_d band that provides AGB values in C (Carbon) Ton/Ha. This data has a resolution of 25 meters, consistent with lower-level GEDI data (L2A for tree height and L2B for tree cover percentage). GEDI L4A data is available from 2019 to 2023 for the region of interest (Follonica). The 2023 dataset will be used as the label for our Pleiades 2024 image, as data

for 2024 is not yet available and in situ measurements are planned to be collected in September 2024 (after the submission of this document). Advancements will be reported in the second release.

Use within the project: as AGB labels for AGB modeling (in this specific case, due to missing in-situ data).

- **ESA WorldCover**

ESA WorldCover is a series of global land cover datasets for the years 2020 and 2021, developed by the European Space Agency (ESA) with a 10-meter resolution. These datasets are derived from Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 satellite imagery and encompass 11 land cover classes, as illustrated in Figure 8, which also provides an overview of land cover in Europe.

Figure 8: ESA World Cover of Europe and Its classes.

Use within the project: valuable reference for generating higher resolution land cover data using Pleiades satellite imagery.

- **In-situ measurements**

Due to delays in acquiring in situ data, no data were received prior to the release of this report. Follow-up will occur in the second release (D4.2).

3.2 Tools and Software

- **QGIS**, or Quantum GIS, is a versatile geographic information system (GIS) software used for spatial analysis, including geospatial data creation, modification, visualization, and analysis. It is particularly adept at vector data manipulation. In this project, QGIS is employed for defining the region of interest, updating the database, and designing layouts. Additionally, it is sometimes used to review satellite imagery.
- **Google Earth Engine** is a cloud-based platform for remote sensing analysis that facilitates various raster analyses and data storage. In this project, Google Earth Engine is utilized for biomass modeling. It also supports multiple machine learning applications, including biomass modeling and evaluation.
- **Scikit-learn**. While Google Earth Engine is efficient for quickly testing and deploying machine learning tasks, Python environments provide a more comprehensive set of tools for machine learning. Scikit-learn, a prominent Python library, offers an extensive suite of tools and modules for preprocessing, modeling, and evaluating complex statistical and machine learning tasks. When Google Earth Engine's capabilities are insufficient, Scikit-learn is used to meet the project requirements.

4. Land Cover

The most common use of satellite imagery in remote sensing is to provide clear visualizations of Earth's landscapes, facilitating a generalized understanding. Within this framework, it is crucial to map observable features of the Earth, such as mountains, forests, farms, rivers, and cities. Satellite imagery serves as a valuable source for extracting this information.

Land cover mapping, classification, or identification refers to the process or methodology used in remote sensing or geography to categorize the types of surface cover on Earth. For example, one area may be classified as urban/concrete, while another may be dominated by grassland. The terms "land cover" and "land use" are often used interchangeably in the context of remote sensing for mapping Earth's landscapes (Verburg, 2006).

4.1 Methodology

There are various methods and approaches for mapping land cover. The most conventional and highest-quality method is digitizing or delineation, which involves manually drawing the borders or polygons of land cover using physical tools or GIS software. This method, also known as manual interpretation, is highly accurate because the mapper directly identifies the land cover classes. However, this approach is time-consuming and labor-intensive, making it less scalable compared to more modern methods.

In the era of machine learning, faster and more scalable methods for land cover mapping have been developed. This method, known as supervised learning or classification, involves digitizing or sampling certain portions of land cover in satellite imagery, rather than the entire image (Enderle, 2005). These samples are then used to train machine learning algorithms or models, which are subsequently applied to the full image. This approach benefits significantly from satellite imagery with multiple spectral bands, which capture unique features not available in RGB images. Additional data sources, such as digital elevation model (DEM), RADAR, or LIDAR, can further enhance the model's performance. Although the results may not achieve the same level of accuracy as manual interpretation, this method is capable of mapping extensive areas and multiple time periods. Figure 9 illustrates the satellite imagery and the resulting land cover classification using this modern machine learning method.

Figure 9: False color composite satellite imagery (left) and classified land cover (right).

In this report, we utilize Pleiades multispectral imagery as the predictor variables and ESA World Cover (EWC) as the labels for land cover, as detailed in the previous chapter on data. Pleiades imagery provides four spectral bands as predictors, and additional variables are generated to improve the model. Specifically, a sharpness metric, calculated as the standard deviation of neighboring pixels within a 3×3 focal operation, is generated. The purpose is to increase the difference between bare land and built-up, in fact these two classes tend to have close spectral reflectance in multispectral imagery. Using sharpness metric, built-up can be distinguished due to its contrast with neighboring pixels while bare land has homogenous pixels surrounding it. Samples from both Pleiades and EWC data are extracted to create a training set and used to train a RF classification model. The trained model then applied to Pleiades imagery is used to obtain higher resolution land cover data at 1.2 meters, compared to the 10-meter resolution of EWC.

To assess accuracy, the data is split into training and testing sets with an 80:20 ratio. The trained model is applied to the test data to evaluate the accuracy of the predictions against the actual labels. The kappa index measures overall accuracy relative to random chance. Overall accuracy and the kappa index are used as assessment metrics.

4.2 Results

A total of 9,000 samples were extracted from Pleiades and EWC data, with 1,000 samples per class. In the study region of Follonica, only 9 out of the 11 possible classes were present, excluding mangrove and moss/lichen. This sample size was determined based on

the minimum number of samples available for any class, ensuring both balanced sample distribution and accurate model assessment. The dataset was divided into training and testing sets, comprising 800 samples for training and 200 samples for testing. The training sets were utilized to train a RF Classification model, using Pleiades multispectral data and sharpness metrics as predictors, and EWC land cover data as labels.

To optimize model performance relative to computational efficiency, various numbers of decision trees were evaluated, with 50 trees determined to provide the best results. The trained model indicated roughly equal importance factors among variables, with each contributing approximately 19% to 21% relative importance in the model's predictive accuracy.

Table 3: Confusion matrix of classified test data compared to the real land cover value.

Prod/User	Tree	Shrub	Grass	Crop	Built-up	Bareland	Snow_and_ice	Water	Wetland
Tree	128	19	9	4	14	1	0	0	6
Shrub	26	80	43	13	13	1	0	0	15
Grass	9	49	69	46	16	5	0	0	7
Crop	6	29	49	108	3	12	0	0	2
Built-up	3	21	5	1	153	13	0	1	6
Bareland	1	1	8	16	21	143	0	3	5
Snow_and_ice	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Water	2	2	0	0	1	4	0	147	26
Wetland	5	21	10	0	9	2	0	15	149

The accuracy of the model was assessed using the test data. A confusion matrix (Table 3) was employed to visualize the land cover classification results, indicating instances where predicted classes differed from actual classifications. In this matrix, the diagonal cells represent true positives, showing the accuracy for each class. Specifically, the classes tree, built-up, bareland, water, and wetland exhibited high correct prediction rates, each surpassing 70%. Conversely, classes such as shrub and grass, which represent lower-level vegetation and potentially overlap, showed lower accuracy levels, each falling below 60%.

Overall, the model achieved an accuracy of 61% across all classes, with a kappa index of 0.565.

Figure 10: Classified land cover for the Italian Living Hub.

Figure 10 depicts the output derived from the satellite imagery processed with the model. The majority of the region is identified as cropland (yellow), consistent with visual observations from the image. Built-up areas predominantly occupy the southern region, particularly near the coast, indicating the presence of a port city. Dense vegetation, characterized by trees and other dense foliage, covers the hilly terrain located in the eastern and northeastern parts of the region.

5. Vegetation Health

Land cover classification typically serves as an initial step rather than a final output in analyses or projects, providing foundational data for more advanced studies. One such application involves monitoring vegetation health, specifically to assess whether specific sections of farmland or forest are experiencing ecosystem stress. Historically, prior to the advent of remote sensing or satellite technology, this analysis relied on manual inspection of plant samples from various locations within the area, as depicted in Figure 11. Results from these inspections were used to identify areas exhibiting the most stress and requiring intervention.

The introduction of remote sensing and drones has enabled faster assessment over larger areas, with drones capable of mapping extensive regions. However, these methods face limitations in scalability, particularly when attempting to cover entire provinces or countries frequently over days, months, or years.

Satellite imagery offers broader spatial coverage and temporal resolution, albeit at the cost of reduced detail. Similarly, drones equipped with multispectral sensors, capable of capturing near-infrared and red edge bands, provide crucial data for monitoring vegetation health. These bands capture detailed information related to plant physiology and chlorophyll content (Zhang, 2016).

Figure 11: NDVI Visualized in Red-White-Green Palette.

5.1 Methodology

The quantification of plant health can be achieved through the utilization of specific spectral bands and wavelengths. A prominent method involves the application of spectral indices, such as the NDVI. The NDVI is defined by the equation:

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR-RED)}{(NIR+RED)}$$

where the red band (RED) exhibits low reflectance in vegetation, in contrast to the NIR (Huang, 2021). This index yields values ranging from -1 to 1, with values below 0 typically indicating water bodies, values between 0 and 0.3 indicating non-vegetated surfaces, and values above 0.3 indicating vegetated areas. An example of such a result is illustrated in Figure 11. Several other indices, such as the EVI, are also available for similar analyses. While NDVI is a valuable tool for monitoring vegetation health, it cannot be used directly to assess plant health across different species or plant types due to their inherent variability. To overcome this limitation, NDVI values should be analyzed in conjunction with a land cover map. By masking NDVI values to specific land cover types, a more accurate assessment of plant health can be achieved. Generally, higher NDVI values correspond to healthier vegetation, whereas lower NDVI values indicate plant stress (Rugel, 2017).

5.2 Results

The multispectral data acquired can be further analyzed using various spectral analysis techniques, such as spectral indices. One widely used index for assessing vegetation health is the NDVI. Additionally, the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) is commonly employed to determine water content in vegetation and for mapping water bodies. These indices can be applied to the acquired imagery and are easily processed and visualized using our application. Figure 12 illustrates the application of both NDVI and NDWI, which can be utilized for subsequent analyses.

Figure 12: NDVI (left) and NDWI (right).

6. Above-ground Biomass

In this chapter, we delve into the domain of Biomass Modelling, a field at the intersection of ecology, remote sensing, and AI. We will explore the data, technologies, and methodologies that underpin AGB Modelling, with a focus on how Remote Sensing and AI are leveraged to enhance our understanding and predictive capabilities.

Biomass in ecology is a term used to describe a whole mass of a species or community of living organisms from a single cell to fully-fledged complex organisms such as humans (Vassilev, 2010). For plants, biomass can be categorized into above and below ground. Above is referring to the biomass above the ground/soil such as the branch and the whole stock where below is below that such as the root.

For the whole planet of Earth, it can be estimated the total biomass will be 546 billion tonnes of carbon where the kingdom of plantae or plant is 82% of that with 450 billion tonnes of carbon (Magnabosco, 2018). Plant can stock a whole lot of carbon due to its ability to ingest CO₂ from the atmosphere and save it in its body. This can be observed from trees where carbon processed becomes part of its stem. This makes the tree one of the carbon sink or capture features in the Earth. This is also the case for vegetation underwater such as seagrass and phytoplankton.

Therefore, with the loss of trees and other vegetation means the capacity of Earth to capture and store carbon decreases. This could mean more carbon in the atmosphere, increasing the temperature (Trumbore, 1996). Due to that, in the modern age, it is important to monitor the vegetation of the earth. This can be done by mapping and modeling to get the biomass data.

Conventionally, biomass can be measured easily by cutting the tree and weighted it. This might be harder to execute if done in a large area or multiple trees. It is also hard and destructive to cut the tree. Other more efficient and less destructive methods are by measuring the DBH and the height then put it in an allometry formula to get the biomass (Réjou-Méchain, 2019). To do it in a large area, some plots will be made as samples, where some trees in the plots will be measured.

All the plot measurements then can be used to calculate biomass based on the measurement such as DBH or height. A formula from trusted sources can be used to

calculate biomass. Such as the equations below from Le Quéré (2017). This equation also needs wood density which sometimes cannot be collected from only field samples. It is usually calculated from cutting and weighing it. Despite that, there is a multiple database of wood density such as from Zane (2009) that can be used as an input.

$$AGB = 0.0673 \times (\rho(DBH)^2 H)^{0.976}$$

ρ = Wood density

DBH = Diameter at Breast Height

H = Height

6.1 Methodology

Preprocessing steps include the step on extracting raster data values using field data sample, machine learning modeling, and evaluation. This step might be redone for every new data that is just acquired to see if there are improvements. Overall summary of the process can be read in Figure 13.

Figure 13: AGB estimation Processing Workflow.

6.1.1 Data Processing

In the data processing section, the objective is to generate features suitable for machine learning training. The training data comprises three primary types: multispectral data, DEM,

including DTM and DSM, and field data. Each data type undergoes specific processing steps to produce the necessary inputs for biomass model training.

The following outlines the three main data types used:

1. Multispectral

The multispectral data processing involves the creation of tree masks, which can be generated using either supervised or unsupervised classification methods. In supervised classification, sample interpretation is employed to label data points as trees or non-trees. In unsupervised classification, tree masks can be generated by applying a threshold to specific spectral indices.

During this process, spectral indices such as the NDVI and NDWI are calculated. NDVI, which utilizes the near-infrared (NIR) and red bands, measures vegetation density. NDWI, which utilizes the green and NIR bands, measures water content. Both the multispectral imagery and the calculated indices are then used as predictors in machine learning training.

2. DEM

By utilizing a DSM and a DTM, object heights can be determined. Subtracting the DTM from the DSM yields an object height model. When this model is further refined using a tree mask derived from the multispectral process, the resulting output is CHM, which indicates tree heights. The CHM is crucial for biomass modeling (Benson, 2020) and can be directly applied using an allometric model or employed as input features in a machine learning model.

3. Field work

Field data includes measurements of tree DBH, both of which are essential variables for calculating AGB. By applying an allometric equation, these measurements are transformed into biomass data. This resultant biomass data is then used as the target variable in the machine learning process.

6.1.2 Machine Learning-based Modeling

In the machine learning phase, geospatial data is utilized to predict biomass based on labeled fieldwork data. Multispectral data, spectral indices, and CHM serve as predictors or

features to train and apply the machine learning model. Fieldwork data is used to extract feature values for training, and is split into training and testing datasets to fit and assess the model, respectively. The machine learning process encompasses data extraction, data splitting, training, and assessment.

The following outlines the four main steps of the methodology:

1. Data Extraction

During data extraction, the values of geospatial data or raster pixels are extracted using fieldwork data. This results in a table with columns representing biomass (label) and predictors (geospatial data).

2. Data Splitting

Data splitting involves dividing the fieldwork data into two groups: training and testing datasets. The training data is used to train the model, while the testing data assesses the model's performance. Typically, a 4:1 ratio is used for training and testing datasets (Vabalas, 2019).

3. Training

In the training step, the training data is fitted using a machine learning model. Several machine learning models, such as RF, SVM, or linear models, are commonly used for biomass prediction (Maulud, 2022). Advanced methods like deep learning or convolutional neural networks can also be employed. The model is trained with the training data, and various models are evaluated to select the most suitable one.

4. Assessment

During the assessment step, the trained model is applied to the testing data predictors. The results are compared with the actual biomass data using metrics such as the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean squared error (RMSE). R^2 measures the correlation between predicted and actual values, ranging from 0 (no correlation) to 1 (perfect correlation), with values above 0.2 indicating some degree of relationship (Renaud, 2010). RMSE indicates the margin of error in actual units (e.g., tons/ha or grams/m²), with lower values signifying better model

performance (Hodson, 2022). The model with the highest R^2 and lowest RMSE is selected as the final model.

6.2 Results

Biomass modeling using machine learning and remote sensing data is a widely utilized method for mapping biomass over large areas. This approach requires satellite imagery, such as the data we have acquired, along with ground truth labels indicating biomass levels in the field for training and testing, and an appropriate machine learning model.

In this project, we aim to model biomass using two different sources of ground truth data: the GEDI dataset from NASA and field data. The GEDI dataset is advantageous because it provides comprehensive information on canopy height, tree cover, and biomass globally across various temporal scales. Although GEDI data does not cover every piece of land but specific ground points, this characteristic makes it ideal for modeling purposes. Furthermore, the GEDI dataset is publicly accessible, making it a more cost-effective alternative to field data. Nevertheless, field data will still be employed to enhance model accuracy and validate the model.

The GEDI dataset is available in several levels that are directly applicable to this project: Level 2A (CHM), Level 2B (tree cover percentage), and Level 4A (biomass). Each of these datasets is used in conjunction with Pleiades multispectral data for training. The results of the modeling using the GEDI dataset are also integrated into the application for easy visualization. Figure 14 displays the modeling outcomes for the CHM, tree cover, and AGB.

Figure 14: CHM (top-left), tree cover (top-right), and above ground biomass (bottom).

However, the model utilizing the GEDI dataset may not yield optimal results due to its 25-meter resolution, compared to our multispectral data with a 0.5-meter resolution. Additionally, the sample size is relatively small, consisting of approximately 700 sample points, with 90% allocated for training and the remaining 10% for testing. The test data is classified using the trained model and compared to the actual reference data to assess accuracy, depicted in a 1-to-1 plot. The results, presented in Figure 15, indicate that all models achieve an accuracy (R^2) of approximately 0.5. This suggests that while the model can predict biomass, its accuracy is limited. Enhanced ground truth data is required to improve the model's performance.

Figure 15: CHM (1st), tree cover (2nd), and AGB (3rd) model accuracy between reference and prediction in 1:1 plot. 1:1 plot line shown in the chart in the red line. Blue trendlines (data x and y relation) that closely position with the red line mean it is more accurate.

7. List of Outputs

The output of Space4Good within the INNO4CFIs WP4 includes a comprehensive report detailing the entire process of data acquisition, processing, and machine learning. Additionally, supplementary outputs such as a biomass map generated from the modeling and a demonstration platform for visualization will be provided to showcase the project's outcomes.

- **Report**

The report serves as the current document outlining the project's background, literature review, methodology, and interim results. It will be released in two phases: an initial progress report and a final comprehensive report that encompasses all completed processes.

- **Satellite-based layers**

Satellite-based layers include a variety of data types, including maps of AGB, land cover classifications, tree height and canopy characteristics, false color composites, and vegetation indices. These layers collectively provide detailed insights into environmental and vegetation characteristics across vast geographical areas, derived from satellite imagery and processed using remote sensing techniques.

- **Geospatial Visualization Platform**

A dedicated platform developed to facilitate user access and visualization of project results. This platform displays biomass maps and statistical tables, accessible via a URL, thereby enabling stakeholders to view results conveniently without the need for specialized software downloads or data loading processes (more details in Appendix C).

Link to the platform: <https://app-inno4cfis-wp4-g52r5pilda-ez.a.run.app/>

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Appendices

- A - Living Hubs Geospatial Data
- B - DCAI 2024 Review Paper
- C - Geospatial Visualization Platform

A - Living Hubs Geospatial Data

The creation and analysis of geospatial data are indispensable components of WP4. Geospatial data refers to information inherently associated with a specific geographic location on the Earth's surface. This geographic context enables a nuanced understanding of spatial relationships, patterns, and trends that is crucial for a wide array of applications, including resource management, urban planning, environmental monitoring, and more specifically in our case, carbon assessment.

INNO4CFIS Living Hubs, as focal points for the project, serve as dynamic ecosystems where the integration of geospatial data and other technologies plays a pivotal role. The geospatial data creation is executed through GIS tools, namely Quantum GIS (QGIS).

Data Structure

To establish a robust foundation for a comprehensive database that aggregates information from diverse partners and locations, our team has undertaken a meticulous endeavor to devise a clear and standardized data structure. The main goal is to ensure sustainability, replicability, and consistency of our data framework for future analyses.

As of today, each plot within the geospatial database is provided with a set of carefully defined properties/fields (Table A1).

Table A1: Field name, description and example for each attribute of the geospatial database.

Field name	Description	Example
id	Unique plot identifier, resulting from the naming convention standard	<i>IT01A20</i>
country	Indicating the country name	<i>Italy</i>

location	Indicating the location name	<i>Santa Paolina, Follonica</i>
location_code	ISO Country Code + numeric code for each specific location assigned by Space4Good	<i>IT01</i>
subsite	One letter indicating the subsite assigned by Space4Good (given for each subsite in alphabetical order)	<i>A</i>
objective	Objective of the plot to specify if it will be used as calibration site of for new plantation	<i>new_plantation</i>
plant_year	Indicating the year where plants were/will be planted	<i>2024</i>
species	Species code	
area (ha)	Numeric value of the area of the plot in hectares	<i>0.150</i>
area (m2)	Numeric value of the area of the plot in square meters	<i>150</i>
perimeter	Numeric value of the perimeter of the plot in meters	<i>200</i>
description	Description of the plot which might content key addition information	<i>sun exposure and slope info</i>

Data Formats

Here are presented some of the key specifics of the data produced.

Geometry: *Polygon (MultiPolygon)*

Coordinate Reference System (CRS): *EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator - Projected*

Formats:

- *ESRI Shapefile* (suggested tool/software: QGIS)
- *geojson* (suggested tool/software: QGIS)
- *KML* (suggested tool/software: QGIS)
- *xlsx* (suggested tool/software: Microsoft excel or Google Sheets)

Naming Convention

To ensure consistency and clarity across the consortium, a standardized naming convention (Figure A1) has been established for uniquely identifying each plot. The convention incorporates [ISO Country Codes](#), the location number (reported in Table A2), the subset code, and the plantation year. This systematic approach guarantees a unified

and comprehensive system for plot identification, fostering effective communication and collaboration within the consortium.

Figure A1: ID Naming Convention.

For example:

- IT01A93 - To uniquely identify the plot in Italy, in Santa Polina, Follonica, Subset A with trees planted in 1993.
- BE01B24 - To uniquely identify the plot in Belgium, in Hensies, Subset B with trees planted in 2024.

We incorporated randomly assigned codes for additional identification within each location (Table A2).

Table A2: Location numbers.

Locations	Country	Number
Santa Paolina, Follonica	Italy	01
Filicaie, Montieri	Italy	02
Castrillo de la Guareña, Zamora	Spain	01
In the Valencia surroundings - TBD	Spain	02
Hensies	Belgium	01
Attika region	Greece	01

This naming convention ensures that each plot is uniquely identified, streamlining communication and data management throughout the consortium.

B - DCAI 2024 Review Paper

The Use of High-Resolution Satellite Imagery and Artificial Intelligence for Above-ground Biomass Modelling in the Mediterranean Region: A Review

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to provide a comprehensive review, based on recently published papers and compare information regarding Above-ground biomass modelling, data sources, methodology, and model accuracy. To fulfill the objectives of the INNO4CFIs project and as an output of this study, we propose utilizing high-resolution surface reflectance data acquired from commercial satellites for index and feature derivation. Integrating Digital Surface Models and Digital Terrain Models derived from Light Detection and Ranging, or Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data, enhances the accuracy of biomass prediction. The Random forest model excels in incorporating multiple features, thus adeptly capturing sample characteristics.

Keywords: Above-ground Biomass, Satellite Imagery, Artificial Intelligence.

1 Introduction

Climate change poses significant challenges to Mediterranean ecosystems, affecting environmental sustainability and socio-economic stability. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2014) highlights the urgent need to address these issues, emphasizing the detrimental impact of emissions from various sources on the delicate ecological balance within the Mediterranean region (Giorgi, 2006).

1.1 Agroforestry to Mitigate Climate Change

In response to these challenges, agroforestry has emerged as a promising strategy to mitigate the effects of climate change through its multifaceted contributions to carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable land management. Numerous scientific studies provide robust evidence supporting the efficacy of agroforestry in climate change mitigation. Agroforestry practices, as outlined by Nair et al. (2009), offer opportunities for carbon sequestration and the enhancement of ecosystem resilience. Additionally, agroforestry promotes biodiversity conservation by providing habitat and food resources for a diverse range of plant and animal species. Asner et al. (2014) demonstrated that agroforestry landscapes support higher levels of biodiversity compared to conventional agricultural systems, thereby contributing to ecosystem resilience in the face of climate change. According to Jose, (2009), agroforestry practices enhance soil fertility, reduce erosion, and provide additional income opportunities for farmers.

1.2 Remote Sensing and AI for Agroforestry AGB

To monitor the carbon sequestration impact of agroforestry practices it becomes necessary to model and estimate the Above-ground biomass (AGB). By quantifying the amount of tree biomass present in agroforestry systems, we can assess their productivity and carbon sequestration potential. This data allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of different agroforestry techniques in enhancing soil fertility, mitigating climate change, and promoting biodiversity. Calculating agroforestry biomass using satellite imagery and Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a sophisticated and accurate approach that has gained traction in recent years. Scientific literature provides compelling evidence supporting the effectiveness of this methodology. Recent advancements in high-resolution remote sensing data and AI techniques have revolutionized biomass estimation (Asner et al., 2014). According to Ploton et al. (2017), Very high spatial resolution (VHSR) optical satellite imagery has demonstrated potential in estimating forest AGB by analyzing canopy texture. Research by Lu et al. (2019) and Fang et al. (2020) showcases the effectiveness of AI methodologies, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and Random

Forest (RF), in analyzing satellite imagery to predict biomass with high precision. These AI-based approaches leverage the wealth of information contained in satellite data to improve the reliability of carbon storage estimations.

By leveraging these technologies, researchers aim to improve the accuracy and efficiency of biomass estimation, facilitating informed decision-making for sustainable resource management (Naidoo & Adam, 2011). However, accurately quantifying biomass in agroforestry systems remains a complex task (Montagnini & Nair, 2004), particularly in the Mediterranean climate, characterized by its unique environmental conditions (Giorgi, 2006) as well as in agroforestry systems, in which trees have very different shapes and growths from those in forests.

1.3 Mediterranean Climate and Biodiversity

The Mediterranean climate supports a remarkable diversity of plant and animal species adapted to its unique environmental conditions. Research by Myers et al. (2000) highlights the Mediterranean Basin as one of the world's biodiversity hotspots, with a wealth of endemic species found in its diverse ecosystems. The region is characterized by mild, wet winters and hot, dry summers. The geo-climatic evolution of the Mediterranean area (especially in the last 100k years) and the fragmented and highly variable environment from a geomorphological and pedoclimatic point of view created a mosaic of habitats ranging from Mediterranean forests to shrublands and coastal ecosystems, fostering high levels of species richness and endemism. Furthermore, the Mediterranean climate significantly influences ecosystem functioning and species interactions. Studies such as Ojeda et al. (2010) demonstrate the role of seasonal rainfall patterns in shaping plant community composition and structure. Variations in precipitation regimes, including droughts and wet periods, can have profound effects on vegetation dynamics, species distribution, and ecosystem resilience.

1.4 INNO4CFIs Project and Objectives of this Study

The project "Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging INNOvations to enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security, and Soil Health" (INNO4CFIs) is a European project co-funded by the European Commission under the Interregional Innovation Investments (I3) instrument (Grant Agreement no. 101115156). INNO4CFIs aims to create a Carbon Farm Technology Platform for peer-to-peer carbon credits exchange as an outcome of the model elaborated on the integration of different technologies: Mangrove Technology, Mycelium-based Technology, Carbon Storage Tracker, Satellite-based technologies, UAV-based technologies and Blockchain-based Solution to be validated in four different living hubs (GR, IT, ES, BE) to increase CO₂ uptake while promoting crucial environmental co-benefits such as sustainable freshwater production, dry-land and soil restoration and biodiversity promotion.

This paper serves as a comprehensive review, synthesizing findings from various scientific literature papers within the framework of the INNO4CFIs project. Through a systematic examination of existing research, we aim to lighten the current state of knowledge regarding biomass calculation methodologies, and the role of high-resolution remote sensing datasets and AI in Mediterranean ecosystems. Ultimately, this synthesis will contribute to advancing our understanding of climate-friendly solutions and guiding future research endeavors to promote resilience to climate change in the Mediterranean regions.

2 Methodology

The methodology employed in this paper follows the systematic review framework delineated by Aromataris (2014), encompassing three primary stages: (1) identification of closely related topics, (2) extraction of pertinent information, and (3) analysis facilitating comprehensive discussion. Figure 1 illustrates the flow of the systematic review flow.

Figure 1. Flow of the systematic review.

This review is dedicated to examining literature related to the utilization of AI in conjunction with high-resolution satellite imagery for AGB within Mediterranean ecosystems. To facilitate the retrieval of relevant literature, specific keywords such as "artificial intelligence", "machine learning", "biomass", "high-resolution imagery", "agroforestry", "Europe", and "Mediterranean" are employed as filters during the literature search process. These keywords are systematically applied across academic databases, including but not limited to Google Scholar, to identify papers that align with the scope of this review.

Subsequently, the extraction of essential information entails the compilation of key data points from the selected papers. Essential information varies depending on the specific focus of the review. In the context of this study, critical information encompasses details regarding the utilized AI or machine learning models, the features or datasets employed for model training, the geographical locations of the research, the habitat, species, or forest types under investigation, and the resultant model outcomes and accuracy metrics. A comprehensive explanation of these extracted data points is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Important Information extracted from each paper analysis.

No	Information	Description
1	AI model	AI or Machine Learning (ML) model used to train and predict biomass. E.g Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random forest.
2	Sample size	How many samples were used to train the model E.g 1000 field samples, 80% for train, 10% for test
3	Data source	Source of data used to train the model such as Landsat, Sentinel-2, Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM), and Field data.
4	Features	Data derived from data sources that are used
5	Land cover type and species	Characteristics of the forest or species being mapped or modeled on such as Mediterranean arid forest, coniferous forest, and beech tree.
6	Location	Location of the research by region or administrative E.g Ede, Netherlands
7	Result/Accuracy	The accuracy or performance of the model E.g R2=0.8

After all pertinent data from the gathered papers are collected, we can start the analysis aimed at discerning patterns, evaluating strengths and weaknesses, and identifying optimal approaches for biomass modelling utilizing AI and high-resolution imagery within Mediterranean regions. This analytical endeavor seeks to elucidate the most viable methodologies for the INNO4CFIs project, thereby facilitating informed decision-making regarding approach selection.

3 Body

3.1 Reviewed Literature Overview and Locations

After conducting the systematic literature search process, a total of 12 papers were selected and included in this review (see Table 2).

Table 2. List of the 12 selected papers reviewed in this article.

Study	Title	Country
Adar et al. (2022)	Estimation of aboveground biomass production using an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) and VEN μ s satellite imagery in Mediterranean and semiarid rangelands	Israel
Fassnacht et al. (2017)	Estimating stand density, biomass, and tree species from very high resolution stereo-imagery - towards an all-in-one sensor for forestry applications?	Germany
Goméz et al. (2012)	Modeling Forest Structural Parameters in the Mediterranean Pines of Central Spain using QuickBird-2 Imagery and Classification and Regression Tree Analysis (CART)	Spain
De Jong et al. (2003)	Above-ground biomass assessment of Mediterranean forests using airborne imaging spectrometry: the DAIS Peyne experiment	France
Kattenborn et al. (2015)	Mapping forest biomass from space - Fusion of hyperspectral EO1-hyperion data and Tandem-X and WorldView-2 canopy height models.	Germany
Lourenco et al. (2021)	Estimating tree aboveground biomass using multispectral satellite-based data in Mediterranean agroforestry system using random forest algorithm	Portugal
Maack et al. (2015)	Modeling forest biomass using Very-High-Resolution data - Combining Textural, spectral and photogrammetric predictors derived from spaceborne stereo images	Germany
Ploton et al. (2017)	Toward a general tropical forest biomass prediction model from very high resolution optical satellite images	Central Africa
Rodriguez-Lozano et al. (2021)	Non-Destructive Biomass Estimation in Mediterranean Alpha Steppes: Improving Traditional Methods for Measuring Dry and Green Fractions by Combining Proximal Remote Sensing Tools	Spain
Santi et al. (2014)	The potential of multifrequency SAR images for estimating forest biomass in Mediterranean areas. Remote Sensing of Environment	Italy
Santi et al. (2017)	Fine-scale spatial distribution of biomass using satellite images	Italy
Vallet et al. (2023)	High resolution data reveal a surge of biomass loss from temperate and Atlantic pine forests	France

3.2 Land Cover Types and Species

The selected list of literature represents a large part of the Mediterranean region. Within the list, there are many papers conducted in southwestern Europe. Regarding the land cover type for which the listed studies aim to estimate AGB, there can be distinguished between four categories; forest, shrublands, (semi) arid rangeland, and agroforestry (see Figure 2). Multiple papers solely rely on satellite-based sensors that focus on estimating AGB in forest areas (Santi, 2017; Goméz, 2012, Kattenborn, 2015; Vallet, 2023) while there are limited papers for other land cover types.

Figure 2. Land Cover type categories in the analyzed research papers.

The complete list contains study areas that in total cover many different species. As mentioned above there are several studies in southwestern Europe. Within this habitat, characterized by relatively low precipitation levels and a temperate climate, study areas predominantly encompass maritime coniferous forests, dryland forests, evergreen oak forests, semi-arid rangelands, and shrublands. Representative species within these categories include Mediterranean Pines, Cypress, Holm Oak, Cork Oak, Downy Oak, Turkey Oak, Laurel, Dogwood, Arbutus, Mastic Tree, and Phillyrea.

For the studies located further north, there are also areas in the context of temperate forests with deciduous and (semi) evergreen tree species included. Species such as Oak, Beech, Hornbeam, and Wild Cherry have been modelled for AGB. Generally, it is observed that most focus in the Mediterranean context goes to evergreen species for AGB modelling applications.

Concerning remote sensing-based AGB modelling for these species, there are several notable characteristics to consider. Relative to the tropical context there is often a lower amount of biomass in these habitats. Also, for evergreen species, there is a lower seasonal fluctuation in chlorophyll content compared to temperate forests. These characteristics hold significant importance in the selection of an appropriate AGB modelling methodology, given the constraints inherent in remote sensing-based approaches. Ploton (2017) summarizes how for two often used data sources for AGB modelling, optical and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellite data, the problem of saturation can occur. Estimated AGB exceeding approximately 150 tons per hectare presents a challenge for optical sensors, as spaceborne sensors lose sensitivity to variations beyond this threshold. Mermoz et al. (2015) illustrates that the saturation point for L-band SAR data typically occurs around 100 tons per hectare. This phenomenon indicates that as canopy density increases, L-band SAR data exhibits a negative correlation with biomass, potentially resulting in significant underestimation of biomass levels.

These examples underscore the variability inherent in different contexts of AGB modelling, necessitating diverse methodological approaches. Furthermore, in Mediterranean contexts, the risk of data saturation in selected remote sensing sources must be evaluated for each AGB modelling application.

3.3 Data and Features

Numerous studies have harnessed diverse datasets to enhance biomass prediction. Data sources such as near-infrared, renowned for their efficacy in extracting vegetation-related information, have frequently been employed for biomass prediction (Price, 1992). This preference is attributed to their capacity to effectively capture characteristics of the stomata layer in foliage, thereby facilitating the derivation of more refined datasets such as vegetation indices, which exhibit heightened correlation with biomass (Zhu, 2015). Nonetheless, the utility of these indices is constrained by certain limitations; they may only be effective in scenarios characterized by uniform tree density, failing to adequately address complexities inherent in environments featuring diverse tree species and age distributions. In such multifaceted contexts, supplementary variables become requisite for accurate biomass prediction.

Figure 3. Data Source in the analyzed research papers.

Figure 3 illustrates that multispectral data obtained from satellite platforms remains a prevalent choice. Specifically, high-resolution multispectral imagery from satellites such as WorldView, SPOT, and QuickBird, augmented with near-infrared bands, enables comprehensive extraction of vegetation-related information, and facilitates the derivation of vegetation indices.

Nevertheless, there is a discernible trend towards the utilization of additional data sources, notably Airborne LiDAR, which has garnered increased attention. LiDAR offers distinct advantages by capturing tree height and structure, in contrast to traditional reflectance-based methods focused solely on tree density (Kwak, 2007). Through the generation of a canopy height model derived from LiDAR data, encompassing both DSM and DTM, detailed insights into tree morphology are obtained.

While Airborne LiDAR boasts high accuracy, its widespread adoption is constrained by the associated costs of sensor acquisition and deployment. Additionally, logistical challenges in mounting LiDAR sensors on satellite platforms, attributable to the considerable distance between satellite orbits and ground surfaces, contribute to its elevated expense. Another noteworthy data source employed in biomass modelling is SAR, which operates as an active remote sensing sensor like LiDAR. SAR technology facilitates the acquisition of detailed information about tree formation and structure through backscatter analysis, thus offering valuable insights for biomass estimation.

Figure 4. Features extrapolated in the analyzed research papers.

While surface reflectance data and DEM datasets, including DSM and DTM, are integral to biomass modelling, additional derived data from surface reflectance holds utility in certain contexts. Figure 4 illustrates datasets such as tasseled caps (TC), which leverage predefined coefficients to characterize the bareness, greenness, and moisture content of an area, serving as alternatives to spectral indices (Haley, 2006). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is another pertinent feature extraction technique, facilitating dimensionality reduction by retaining only the most informative data from a dataset, thereby enabling biomass prediction with minimal features (Patel, 2010). Additionally, incorporating land cover data can enhance model accuracy by enabling species-specific modelling, thereby refining predictions. Variables such as density, structure, and Leaf Area Index (LAI), derived from a combination of field measurements, DEM data, and spectral reflectance, can further augment biomass mapping efforts. However, it is imperative to consider the scope of modelling, encompassing

factors such as sample size and geographic extent, to ensure the robustness and applicability of the developed models.

3.4 Models and Accuracy Assessment

Various modelling techniques are employed in biomass estimation, ranging from simplistic linear regression to intricate artificial neural networks. These models incorporate a diverse array of features and sample sizes, factors which may affect influence beyond the model structure itself. Consequently, generalizing the performance of each model without standardization of parameters may prove suboptimal. Nonetheless, understanding how each model performs in estimating biomass provides important insights into finding the best modeling approach.

Figure 5. Median R² and RMSE of machine learning models on biomass. The number for each model shows the amount of times the selected studies used it.

Despite the potentially disparate and limited number of models analyzed, discerning overarching trends remains paramount. Aggregating data from various papers, the coefficient of determination (R²), and root mean square error (RMSE) for each model were plotted, with subsequent calculation of the median values, as depicted in Figure 5. The utilization of median values serves to mitigate the influence of outliers (Zawojewski, 2000). Linear regression continues to demonstrate noteworthy performance owing to its ability to capture the high correlation between select variables and biomass, a phenomenon well-documented in prior research (Santi, 2014; De Jong, 2003). Specifically, the correlation between normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and biomass underscores its efficacy. However, while exhibiting a median R² of 0.8, the accuracy of linear regression may be understated due to the limited sample size. Random forest emerges as the most frequently employed model within the reviewed literature. Renowned for its adaptability and robustness in remote sensing applications (Belgiu, 2016), this model is extensively employed across various research domains, encompassing both land cover classification and thematic parameter regression. Its adaptability stems from its decision forest architecture, which diverges from conventional methodologies such as support vector machines or regression by employing a multitude of conditional branches based on feature-value thresholds. This approach facilitates binary decisions, enhancing interpretability, although at the expense of increased susceptibility to overfitting.

Random forest regression exhibits a median R² of 0.74, a figure comparatively lower than linear regression models. Despite this, an accompanying RMSE of 14 ton/ha underscores its efficacy, particularly in dense forest environments where biomass typically ranges between 200 and 400 ton/ha (Yang, 2020). The RMSE value, when contextualized within this range, signifies a favorable error rate of under 10%, indicative of the model's high accuracy. Recently, many scientific studies have been using deep learning in various areas of remote sensing. Deep learning involves complex models that mimic human thinking, like artificial neural networks and convolutional neural networks (LeCun, 2015). Within the examined literature focusing on biomass estimation utilizing high-resolution imagery, instances of deep-learning model utilization were identified. Specifically, Vallet (2023) and Santi (2017) employed artificial neural networks and U-Net architectures, respectively, for this

purpose. The objective was to assess the efficacy of deep learning methodologies in biomass estimation relative to conventional approaches. Preliminary findings suggest that deep learning methods may exhibit less performance compared to conventional models. For instance, when contrasted with RF, deep learning models display a notably higher median RMSE of 40 ton/ha compared to 20 ton/ha. Although deep learning models may yield marginally higher R^2 values (0.8 compared to 0.74 for RF), the disparity is not substantial. This observation may be attributed to factors such as limited sample size or discrepancies in feature selection methodologies.

4 Conclusions

4.1 Significance of Data and Features

While numerous features and datasets hold potential for biomass modelling, only select ones prove pivotal. Foundational data such as surface reflectance, while versatile, may not always encompass the information required for robust modelling. Nevertheless, its utilization remains crucial, as it offers nuanced pixel values reflective of diverse environmental characteristics. In scenarios where model complexity precludes the incorporation of numerous features, indices derived from surface reflectance can serve as viable alternatives. Furthermore, data derived from independent sources such as LiDAR and SAR provide valuable supplementary information beyond that attainable from surface reflectance data alone. These sources offer detailed insights into vegetation height and texture. Particularly, LiDAR data enables the generation of canopy height models, a critical parameter for accurate AGB estimation, given the significant role of height in the calculation.

4.2 Optimal Model Accuracy Evaluation

The quality of a model is inherently contingent upon the quality of its input data, thereby emphasizing the paramount importance of features and samples. While this assertion remains valid, it is also imperative to consider the adaptability of the model in question. Among available models, the RF model exhibits remarkable adaptability and possesses the capacity to effectively accommodate multiple features compared to linear models. Additionally, it does not necessitate a larger volume of samples relative to deep learning models. Consequently, the RF model emerges as the most suitable option when utilizing multiple features as predictors.

4.3 Optimal Configuration for the INNO4CFIs project

The INNO4CFIs project will leverage high-resolution surface reflectance data obtained from commercial satellites, facilitating the generation of various indices and derived datasets. Additionally, the project aims to incorporate high-resolution DSM and DTM obtained from LiDAR technology. These datasets can be further processed to derive a canopy height model, or SAR data will be considered as supplementary features for biomass prediction. Within the INNO4CFIs project timeline, the launch of the new ESA BIOMASS mission is scheduled for 2024 (ESA website). This P-band radar sensor designed for biomass estimations from space will support future improvements in AGB modelling which can be explored during the project. Given the utilization of multiple features, the RF model emerges as a pragmatic choice due to its capacity to adaptively construct a well-fitted model tailored to the provided samples and features.

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C - Geospatial Visualization Platform

The geospatial data presented in the previous section can only be visualized and utilized within geospatial software such as QGIS or Google Earth Engine. To facilitate access for non-specialist users, a web application or mobile app is required to display the visualized data in an intuitive and user-friendly manner.

Link to the platform: <https://app-inno4cfis-wp4-g52r5pilda-ez.a.run.app/>

Figure C1: Geospatial Visualization Platform.

As part of WP4, we have developed a geospatial visualization platform to showcase our results through a web application. This application integrates web maps and provides access to the data. The app layout, depicted in Figure C1, is built on the Next.js framework, a comprehensive full-stack web framework. It leverages the Google Earth Engine API for data processing, enabling the visualization of data tiles on the map. The application is deployed on Google Cloud Run, a serverless container service.

The application layout consists of three main components: the map, legend, and panel. The map, occupying 80% of the layout, serves as the primary interface for data visualization. The legend provides essential information about the data, such as color meanings. The panel, located on the rightmost side of the layout, allows users to change the region or plot, select the date of the data, and choose the type of layer to display.

Currently, the application supports the visualization of one region and one date. However, multiple layers can be visualized on the map, including true color, false color, NDVI, NDWI,

canopy height, canopy cover, biomass, and land cover. Users can easily switch between layers by selecting the desired option, as shown in Figure C2 (left). When a layer is changed, the legend also updates accordingly, as illustrated in Figure C2 (right) for land cover.

Figure C2: Choosing a Layer (left) and legend for land cover (right).

By clicking on a plot displayed on the map, users can view detailed plot information for the selected layer, as illustrated in Figure C3. Future iterations will include additional data, such as biomass information and other layer-specific data, enhancing the application's utility and comprehensiveness.

Figure C3: Plot information pop up window.